

Potentiometric Study of Humic Acid Metal Interactions

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Potentiometric study of synthetic and natural humic acid (H. A.) fractions and their derivatives (nitro-, sulphonated and phosphorylated) in presence of heavy metal ions show the formation of ligand-metal complexes. The order and magnitude of pH -drop indicate the following order $Fe^{2+} > Al^{3+} > Cu^{2+} > Pb^{2+}$ in metal-ligand interactions. Of the various ligands, the complex formation capacity follows the order phosphorylated organic matter (o.m.) > nitrated o.m. > sulphonated o.m.

SOIL organic matter metal interactions play an important role in plant nutrition process, hence a study of such interactions is useful for prediction of the fate of a particular metal ion in soil.

All metal chelates may be considered as formed by the displacement of one or more weak acidic protons of the ligand by the metal ion, as a result, there is a drop in pH when chelate formation takes place. The greater the tendency of a metal ion to chelate with a particular organic ligand, the greater is the drop in pH (Martell and Chaberk¹). Schnitzer and his co-workers² have shown that many metal ions undergo complexation with soil organic matter. Recently Adhikari and Hazra³ have studied soil o.m. -metal interactions and are of opinion that hydroxylated type of metal-organic matter complexes are formed.

The object of the present paper is to investigate the interactions of different bi- and tri-valent metal ions with natural and synthetic H. A. fractions and their different derivatives viz. nitro, sulphonated and phosphorylated products.

Experimental

Natural H. A. is extracted from Kalimpong soil (0-15 cm depth), Darjeeling. The sodium carbonate extract

is coagulated with HCl (pH 2.0) and different fractions are separated using standard procedure^{4,18}. The H. A. is dialysed against distilled water and then electro-dialysed. The fraction is then repeatedly resin treated and finally dialysed against H-resin (I.R.-12) to get H. A. hydrogen form.

Synthetic H. A. is prepared by the condensation of hydroquinone and glycine between pH 8.0 and 9.0 by refluxing in water bath for about 8 to 10 hours following the procedure of Coulson⁵. The contents are then precipitated with 1(M) HCl and H. A. fraction is separated by the usual procedure⁴.

H. A. is sulphonated by BF_3/H_2SO_4 at 100° for about 90 minutes following the method of Mitsun⁶. It is nitrated by 15% HNO_3 with 5 times its weight of crude H. A. at 80° for two hours with constant shaking, and phosphorylated⁸ with monosodium hydrogen phosphate at 100° under reduced pressure and then treated with water. The different derivatives are thoroughly dialysed, electro-dialysed and repeatedly resin treated to get as their hydrogen form. The chemical analyses and average molecular weight of different o.m. are given in Table-1.

TABLE 1—ORGANIC MATTER

	Kalimpong soil (0-15 cm depth) Darjeeling Dt. West Bengal, India								
	H. A.	Nitro H.A.	Sulphonated H.A.	Phosphorylated H.A.	H.A.	Nitro H.A.	Sulphonated H.A.	Phosphorylated H.A.	
Average mol. wt.	1020	850	1250	1860	2050	1680	2640	3260	
%Carbon	48.2	48.18	45.32	44.45	52.31	47.51	49.45	48.31	
%Hydrogen	5.18	6.22	3.15	3.20	7.02	9.02	6.02	5.95	
%Nitrogen	1.95	3.14	2.01	2.02	5.05	6.12	3.86	3.52	
%Sulphur	—	—	1.12	—	—	—	1.85	—	
%Phosphorous	—	—	—	0.96	—	—	—	1.20	

To a known amount of o.m. (o.m.=H. A. synthetic or natural, and their different derivatives), 2.0 ml of 0.01(N) NaCl are added and the volume is made upto 10.0 ml with distilled water. The sol is then titrated cautiously with standard NaOH solution and the corresponding pH of the sol is noted with a Cambridge pH meter at 30° equipped with a Cambridge glass electrode and a saturated calomel electrode with an aqueous agar-agar-KCl (saturated) salt bridge. In a similar way same amount of different o.m. in presence of metal salts ($\text{Fe}^{3+}/\text{Al}^{3+}/\text{Cu}^{2+}$ as chloride and Pb^{2+} nitrate) required to form metal organic matter complexes are also titrated in a similar way by NaOH solution. Metal salt solutions are also titrated with NaOH. Mole ratios of o.m. metal ions used for preparation of the complexes are calculated from these potentiometric titration figures which are not shown here.

Different titration curves (not shown here) show the drop in pH (hence inflection in titration curves) and indicate the formation of metal-, ligand complexes^{1,2}. The metal salt solutions are fairly acidic, initial drop in pH is not due to free metal ions, metal ions interact with the functional sites like CO-OH grs- OH grs of the ligands liberating protons for which the initial pH drop is observed. According to these earlier workers, greater the tendency of the metal ions to form chelates, the greater is pH drop and vary markedly with metal ions. The potentiometric titration, therefore, provides useful information regarding chelation reaction. However, there is a limitation in this study e.g. one should have a clear idea regarding molecular structure of the ligand (monodentate or bidentate) which is not known in the case because of the heterogeneity in structure. In spite of this, the study has its importance. Thus Fraser¹⁵ from his study concluded that accumulation of toxic amounts of Cu in a forest peat was due to a sequence

of events that included uptake of Cu from surrounding mineral soil by plant root, up ward translocation into leaf tissue in cooperation into humus layer of soil and transport to the swamp in seepage water as soluble organic complex. Coleman⁹ observed that that Cu^{2+} displaced the titration curves of acid washed peat and stated as due to the complex formation which were corroborated by others. According to them the formation of water soluble hydroxylated complexes in H. A. metal interactions is the cause of pH drop.

In this study the magnitude of pH drop upon addition of different metal ions follows the order $\text{Fe}^{3+} > \text{Al}^{3+} > \text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{Pb}^{2+}$, which is in accordance with the results of earlier workers¹². In the present study it is noted that sulphonated and nitrated H. A. possess lower tendencies to combine with a given metal ion than that of the original o.m., on the other hand phosphorylation markedly increased the chelate forming tendency of the o.m. It is, however, known¹⁰ that nitro- and sulphonic acid groups are electron acceptors and if they are linked directly to benzene ring, the acidity of the phenolic hydroxyl group increases and the basicity of $-\text{NH}_2$ group decreases. Due to this coordinating tendencies of these groups are lowered. Hence it appears that these groups have taken their positions in the aromatic core of H. A. and thus have effects on the coordinating groups. On phosphorylation, in addition to the already present groups, phosphorus enters into complex formation with metal ions. The stability of the complexes thus increases. In order to get an idea about the mechanism of these reactions between o.m. and metal ions, number of protons released by NaOH during the titration of o.m. and mixture of o.m. and metal ions are calculated and reported in Tables 2 and 3.

TABLE 2—PROTONS RELEASED PER MOLE OF ORGANIC MATTER (H.A.)

pH	Kalimpong H.A.	Kalimpong Sulpho-H.A.	Kalimpong Nitro-H.A.	Kalimpong Phospho-H.A.	Synthetic H.A.	Synthetic Sulpho-H.A.	Synthetic Nitro-H.A.	Synthetic Phospho-H.A.
4.0	—	1.84	—	—	—	—	—	—
4.5	—	2.76	—	—	0.87	0.40	0.56	—
5.0	1.65	3.5	1.38	0.95	2.18	1.8	1.7	—
5.5	2.83	4.6	2.48	2.2	3.65	4.0	2.3	0.50
6.0	3.67	6.44	3.2	2.4	4.9	6.4	3.4	1.00
6.5	4.75	7.3	4.00	2.8	5.6	8.0	4.5	1.4
7.0	5.41	9.6	4.60	3.2	6.4	8.6	5.1	1.6
7.5	5.80	11.96	5.0	3.5	7.3	9.4	5.6	1.9
8.0	6.16	—	5.5	3.96	8.2	10.2	6.2	2.2
8.5	6.9	—	6.3	4.8	9.4	12	—	2.8
9.0	8.0	—	7.7	—	—	—	—	3.96

From Table 2 it is evident that at pH 5.5, approximately three COOH groups, at pH 7.5 and at pH 8.0 six -COOH groups are neutralised for Kalimpong H. A. At pH 9.0 in addition to six-COOH groups two phenolic hydroxyl groups are also neutralised. On sulphonation greater number of protons are released per mole of o.m. at any particular pH, in comparison to those released from H. A. alone. But on nitration and phosphorylation number of protons released per mole of o.m. decreases. This probably is due to the fact that on sulphonation, additional number of acid sulphonic groups are introduced in the H. A. molecule. Sulphuric acid behaves both as an oxidising as well as a sulphonating agent. Perhaps due to the oxidising character of the acid, the phenolic and to some extent the -COOH groups have been oxidised and -SO₃H groups have taken their places in the aromatic core of humic acid molecules or it may so happen that sulphuric acid may enter the vacant positions in benzene ring. If this happens, then the acidic properties of humic acid will show an increase in value in the way :

But on nitration, because of the oxidising property of HNO₃, some breakdown of H. O. A. structure (as appeared in decrease in average mol. wt.) might have occurred causing a decrease in carboxylic groups. On phosphorylation, phenolic hydroxyl groups are blocked by phosphoryl groups, possibly some change in the structure of H. A. might have taken place. It appears that simple reaction of phosphoric acid by the phenolic hydroxyl group would show an increase in acidic property of the phosphorylated product as

But, no such effect noticed in this case and hence such simple reaction does not take place. Due to the complex structure of humic acids, a number of phenolic-OH groups simultaneously interact with the phosphoric acid, the resultant effect will be the decrease in acidity of the product.

R = aromatic core of humic acid

Similar observations are noted in titrating synthetic H. A. and its different derivatives, namely sulphonated, nitrated and phosphorylated products as shown in Table 2.

The difference of protons set free from different o.m. metal complexes can be explained by writing the following simplified equations as suggested earlier^{2,3,14}

(a) When no metal ions are added—

R = H. A. without six - COOH groups

R = Nitro H.A. without four to five - COOH groups.

R = H. A. without four - SO₃H and five - COOH groups.

When M²⁺ salt is added—

When M³⁺ salt is added—

Similar types of reactions with metal ions and nitrohumic acid most probably take place. Reactions of metal ions with sulphonated H. A. may proceed in the following way :

(i) with bi-valent metal ions :

or

(ii) with tri-valent metal ions :

The number of protons released from the sulfonated product by titration with NaOH may be explained by these probable reactions. This does not bear any relation to the molecular weight of the complexes. Reactions bi- or tri-valent metal ions with phosphorylated derivative could not be depicted as above because how the phosphoryl groups enter into reactions with different metal ions could not be definitely ascertained from the present study.

TABLE 3—PROTONS RELEASED PER MOLE OF METAL ADDED FROM

pH	Kalimpong H.A. by				Kalimpong Sulpho H.A. by				Kalimpong Nitro-H.A. by				Kalimpong Phospho-H.A. by			
	Pb ²⁺	Cu ²⁺	Al ³⁺	Fe ³⁺	Pb ²⁺	Cu ²⁺	Al ³⁺	Fe ³⁺	Pb ²⁺	Cu ²⁺	Al ³⁺	Fe ³⁺	Pb ²⁺	Cu ²⁺	Al ³⁺	Fe ³⁺
4.5	—	—	—	—	—	0.99	1.40	1.46	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
5.0	0.48	0.80	1.80	2.00	0.66	1.21	1.90	1.95	0.80	1.00	1.80	1.60	0.56	0.33	1.54	2.57
5.5	-0.52	0.96	1.80	1.88	0.88	1.54	2.30	2.68	0.92	1.08	1.80	1.60	0.46	0.26	1.43	1.95
6.0	-1.50	0.96	1.98	1.90	1.23	1.54	2.40	1.59	1.90	1.60	2.00	1.60	0.67	0.56	1.87	1.95
6.5	-1.48	0.90	1.73	2.00	2.2	1.76	2.60	2.01	—	1.50	2.50	1.74	0.96	0.81	2.31	1.951.11
7.0	-1.70	1.12	2.34	2.90	—	—	2.90	3.17	—	1.50	2.62	1.81	1.11	0.91	2.64	2.1
7.5	—	1.60	3.24	—	—	—	—	—	—	1.80	2.82	2.00	1.11	0.32	3.24	—
8.0	—	2.24	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	2.00	—	2.61	—	1.58	—	—

pH	Synthetic H.A. from				Sulpho Synthetic H.A. from				Nitrated Synthetic H.A. from				Phospho Synthetic H.A. from			
	Pb ²⁺	Cu ²⁺	Al ³⁺	Fe ³⁺	Pb ²⁺	Cu ²⁺	Al ³⁺	Fe ³⁺	Pb ²⁺	Cu ²⁺	Al ³⁺	Fe ³⁺	Pb ²⁺	Cu ²⁺	Al ³⁺	Fe ³⁺
4.5	—	0.88	1.73	1.60	—	0.80	1.40	1.85	—	0.91	1.41	1.69	—	—	—	—
5.0	1.05	1.18	1.83	1.70	0.80	1.20	2.20	2.59	0.63	1.08	1.80	1.90	—	—	—	—
5.5	1.17	1.03	1.83	1.50	1.0	2.00	2.80	—	0.72	0.92	2.20	2.38	0.43	0.84	1.74	1.93
6.0	1.40	1.18	1.83	1.44	2.2	2.30	3.00	—	0.72	1.08	2.40	2.85	0.37	0.94	1.99	2.17
6.5	1.30	1.18	2.40	1.70	—	2.32	3.00	—	1.44	1.08	2.60	—	0.37	0.98	2.03	2.32
7.0	1.30	1.03	—	1.93	—	2.00	—	—	1.80	1.26	2.90	—	0.64	1.03	2.13	2.60
7.5	—	1.18	—	2.5	—	2.22	—	—	—	1.44	—	—	0.74	1.05	2.26	2.72
8.0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	1.44	—	—	0.80	1.05	2.46	2.83
8.5	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.96	2.17	—	2.83

On comparison of data in Table 3 with the above reactions it may be said that the complex formation between natural H. A. and synthetic H. A. with divalent metal ions proceeds according to the equation (c) between pH 4.5 to 7.0 for natural H. A. and between pH 4.5. to 7.5 for synthetic preparations, since approximately one proton is released per mole of metal added within this pH range. In this pH- range Cu^{2+} is present as $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})^+$ and Pb^{2+} which form electrovalent bonds with negatively charged carboxyl groups. The results corroborate the earlier findings of Khanna and Stevenson¹¹. It is also observed that upto pH 7.0 for natural H. A. and upto pH 7.5 for synthetic preparation, the complexes with Pb^{2+} and Cu^{2+} are stable. Above this pH these complexes break down releasing approximately two protons per mole of metal added according to the equation (d).

TABLE 4—PROTONS RELEASED PER MOLE OF METAL ION FROM

pH	Pb ²⁺	Cu ²⁺	Al ³⁺	Fe ³⁺
4.0	1.69	—	—	0.76
4.5	1.95	—	—	1.52
5.0	2.08	—	1.4	2.83
5.5	2.20	0.47	1.84	3
6.0	—	1.01	2.21	—
6.5	—	1.66	2.53	—
7.0	—	1.92	2.90	—

Reactions of bi-valent metal ions with sulphonated and nitrohumic acids (both natural and synthetic preparations) appear to be similar in nature except that for sulphonated product the complex breaks above pH 5.0 (both for Kalimpong sulpho H. A. and synthetic preparations). However, with nitro- H. A. the complex is stable upto pH 5.5 for natural product and upto pH 7.0 for synthetic nitro-H. A. In case of phosphorylated H. A. (both natural and synthetic preparations) it is observed that the complex with Cu^{2+} is highly stable upto pH 8.0 above which it however breaks up, with Pb^{2+} the complex is stable upto pH 7.0.

The situation with trivalent metal ions may be explained as follows :

Natural o.m. reacts with Al^{3+} according to the equation (g) where Al^{3+} is present as $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_2^+$ and between pH 5.0 to 7.0 approx. 2.0 protons are released per mole of metal. Reaction of Al^{3+} with

synthetic o.m. occurs according the equation (f) where Al^{3+} is present as $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_2^+$ and between pH 4.5 to 6.0 approx. 1.0 to 1.5 protons are thus released per mole of metal. Above pH 6.0 and upto pH 7.0 Al^{3+} is probably present as $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3^0$ as approx. 2.0 protons are released per mole of metal and the reaction seems to proceed according to the equation (g). Reaction with Fe^{3+} seems to be similar to that for Al^{3+} where approximately 2.0 protons are released per mole of Fe^{3+} within the pH range 4.5 to 7.0 when Fe^{3+} is present as $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2^+$. For sulphonated and nitrated products although similar types of reactions occur but the complexes break down at lower pH. Comparatively nitro-product are more complexing agent than sulphonated products. Trivalent metal ions from stable complexes with phosphorylated o.m. and the complexes are stable upto higher pH range e.g. for Fe^{3+} complex upto pH 7.0 for natural derivative and upto pH 8.0 for synthetic derivative.

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